

BARRIERS TO EFFECTIVE TIME MANAGEMENT AND THEIR RELATIONSHIP WITH EXAMINATION ANXIETY AMONG FINAL-YEAR STUDENTS AT FATIMA COLLEGE OF NURSING SCIENCES SIFAWA

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ABSTRACT

Background: Time management is a critical skill for nursing and midwifery students balancing academic demands and clinical responsibilities. Poor time management may contribute to elevated levels of examination anxiety, thereby affecting academic performance and mental well-being.

Objective: To identify the barriers to effective time management and examine their relationship with examination anxiety among final-year nursing and midwifery students at Fatima College of Nursing Sciences, Sifawa.

Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted among all 97 final-year students enrolled in the 2024/2025 academic session. A structured self-administered questionnaire with five sections was used. Data were analyzed using SPSS v25. Descriptive statistics summarized participant responses, while Pearson correlation and chi-square tests assessed relationships between variables.

Results: Key time management barriers included poor planning ($M=3.67$), distractions ($M=3.45$), and procrastination ($M=3.42$). Examination anxiety levels were moderate to high among 63% of respondents. A significant positive correlation ($r=0.419$, $p<0.01$) was found between time management barriers and examination anxiety. Chi-square tests showed significant associations between gender, program of study, and anxiety levels ($p<0.05$).

Conclusion: Ineffective time management significantly contributes to examination anxiety among final-year nursing and midwifery students. Targeted interventions are recommended to improve students' planning skills and reduce academic stress.

Keywords: Time management, Examination anxiety, Nursing students, Midwifery, Nigeria, Academic stress

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Effective time management—the ability to plan, prioritize, monitor, and allocate time to tasks is therefore widely recognized as a foundational academic skill that supports learning, clinical competence, and psychological well-being (Mohamadkhani Ghiasvand et al., 2017). Yet many nursing students struggle to manage time effectively. When time-management difficulties combine with high-stakes testing and clinical performance demands, they can contribute to pronounced examination (test) anxiety — a situation-specific form of performance anxiety that impairs concentration, memory retrieval, and test performance (Khaira et al., 2023).

Cross-sectional and intervention studies among nursing students consistently show negative associations between time-management skills and anxiety: students with stronger planning and time-use behaviors report lower state and trait anxiety scores, while time management training is associated with reductions in stress and improved academic motivation (Mohamadkhani Ghiasvand et al., 2017; Lin et al., 2025). Mechanistically, poor time management increases the frequency of last-minute studying, reduces exposure to formative testing (practice), and produces unpredictable preparation patterns; these conditions increase uncertainty and negative expectations at exam time, which in turn trigger cognitive interference (worry), autonomic arousal, and memory retrieval failures that manifest as test anxiety (Khaira et al., 2023).

A recent systematic review and meta analysis by Thi Nhi Vo, Hsiao Yean Chiu, Yeu Hui Chuang, and Hui Chuan Huang (2023) synthesized data from 121 studies worldwide and found that nursing students

experienced moderate levels of stress (42.1%) and mild to moderate levels of anxiety (19.4–25.1%) during examinations, with third and fourth year students showing higher levels of severe stress compared to their junior counterparts (29.0% vs. 15.1%). In Malaysia, Manjit Kaur Khaira, Raja Lexshimi Raja Gopal, Suriati Mohamed Saini, and Zaleha Md Isa (2024) surveyed 421 nursing students and reported that 25.4% had moderate test anxiety while 2.1% experienced severe anxiety, underscoring the pervasive nature of exam related distress even in private institutions.

In sub Saharan Africa, studies consistently report elevated anxiety among nursing trainees. In Gauteng Province, South Africa, a cross sectional survey by Manana Ntuli, Thembelihle Arendse, Kumetsa Mokwena, and Katlego Maaga (2023) found a 74.7% prevalence of anxiety symptoms among nursing students, with 19.5% experiencing severe anxiety. In Nigeria, Chibueze Anosike, Chigozie G. Anene Okeke, Ebere E. Ayogu, and Mariagorathy C. Oshigbo (2022) reported that 61.7% of first year pharmacy, medical, and nursing students experienced anxiety, although only 24.9% were willing to seek professional psychological help. A subsequent study at Ahmadu Bello University in Zaria found that 68.1% of health sciences students (including 58 nursing students) reported varying degrees of anxiety (mild to extremely severe) during the 2023–2024 academic session.

Studies globally and locally (Akintola, 2020; Musa & Dogo, 2022) have found a significant link between time mismanagement and academic pressure among health science students. However, there is limited evidence from rural-based nursing colleges in Northern Nigeria, such

as Fatima College of Nursing Sciences, Sifawa. This study addresses this gap by identifying common time management barriers and evaluating their relationship with examination anxiety in this unique context.

The main objective of this study is to assess the Barriers to Effective Time Management and Their Relationship with Examination Anxiety among Final-Year Nursing and Midwifery Students at Fatima College of Nursing Sciences, Sifawa. The specific objectives are; to identify the common barriers to effective time management among final-year nursing and midwifery students at the college, to assess the level of examination anxiety experienced by final-year nursing and midwifery students at the college, to examine the relationship between time management challenges and examination anxiety at the College to suggest possible strategies to improve time management skills and reduce exam-related anxiety among nursing and midwifery students at the College.

2.0 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 STUDY DESIGN AND SETTING

A descriptive cross-sectional design was used. The study was conducted at Fatima College of Nursing Sciences, Sifawa, Sokoto State, Nigeria. The college offers three-year diploma programs in Nursing and Midwifery and admits approximately 120 students annually. Final-year cohorts typically comprise 35–45 students per program.

2.2 STUDY POPULATION AND SAMPLING

The target population comprised all 97 final-year students enrolled in the 2024–2025 academic year: 48 from General Nursing and 49 from Basic Midwifery. A census sa-

mping method was employed since the population was below 200, in line with Bukar (2011).

2.3 DATA COLLECTION INSTRUMENT

A structured, self-administered questionnaire was used. It had five sections in which a likert scale range from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree) was also used. Section A: Demographics (age, gender, program, marital status, GPA) Section B: Time management barriers (15 Likert-scale items) Section C: Examination anxiety (10 Likert-scale items) Section D: Perceived links between time barriers and anxiety (5 items) Section E: Willingness to adopt strategies (5 items)

2.4 VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY

Face and content validity were established through expert review by the project supervisor and student feedback. The reliability index was 0.70 using the test-retest method with Pearson correlation over a two-week interval from the first test and second test.

2.5 DATE COLLECTION PROCEDURE

The questionnaire was distributed electronically via class WhatsApp groups and institutional email. Students were informed about the purpose of the study and assured of confidentiality. Data were collected over one week with follow-up reminders.

2.6 DATA ANALYSIS

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, means, standard deviations) were used for summary. Pearson correlation

tested the relationship between time management barriers and anxiety. Chi-square tests assessed associations with demographic variables. Significance was set at $p=0.05$.

2.7 ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

Ethical clearance was obtained from College. Written informed consent was obtained electronically. Participation was voluntary, and anonymity and confidentiality were maintained throughout.

3.0 RESULTS

3.1 DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE OF RESPONDENTS (N=97)

Variables	Catigory	F	%
Age	17-20	22	22.7
	21-24	43	44.3
	>25	32	33.0
Gender	Male	18	17.4
	Female	79	76.6
Program	Nursing	48	49.5
	Midwifery	48	50.5
Marital status	Single	81	83.5
	Married	13	13.4
	Divorce/Widow	3	3.1
Prior academic performance	GPA ≥ 3.5	28	28.9
	GPA 2.5-3.49	53	54.6
	GPA < 2.5	16	16.6

Among the 97 respondents, the majority (44.3%) were aged 21–24, female (76.6%), split evenly between nursing and midwifery, predominantly single (83.5%), and most reported GPAs ≥ 2.5 (83.5%).

3.2 BARRIERS To EFFECTIVE TIME MANAGEMENT

Key reported barriers included:

Poor planning (M = 3.67), Procrastination (M = 3.42), Social distractions (e.g., phone use) (M = 3.45) and Overlapping clinical schedules and academic work (M = 3.31)

3.3 LEVELS OF EXAMINATION ANXIETY

63% of students reported moderate to high

anxiety levels. Common symptoms included:

Excessive worry before exams (M = 3.61), Sweating or rapid heartbeat during exams (M = 3.49) and Inability to focus while studying (M = 3.27)

3.4 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TIME MANAGEMENT BARRIERS AND ANXIETY

A significant positive correlation was found between time management barriers and examination anxiety: Pearson $r = 0.419$, $p = < 0.001$

3.5 ASSOCIATION WITH DEMOGRAPHICS

Chi-square tests revealed:

Gender was significantly associated with anxiety levels ($\chi^2 = 5.742$, $p = 0.017$)

Program of study was also significantly associated ($\chi^2 = 4.111$, $p = 0.043$)

4.0 DISCUSSION

This study confirms that poor time management is a strong contributor to examination anxiety among final-year nursing and midwifery students, aligning with findings by Alabi et al. (2021) and Tunde et al. (2019). The positive correlation suggests that as time-related stress increases, so does test anxiety.

Barriers like poor planning, distractions, and workload were particularly influential. These findings mirror studies by Musa & Dogo (2022), who highlighted smartphone addiction and conflicting schedules as primary time drains in Nigerian colleges.

The higher anxiety among female students and nursing program participants may reflect the differing workload expectations and cultural stressors placed on female learners or those in more academically intense tracks, consistent with findings by Onyeizugbo (2010) and Bayram and Bilgel (2008), who reported that female university students tend to experience higher anxiety due to societal role expectations and emotional stress burdens.

5.0 CONCLUSION

Time management barriers significantly influence examination anxiety among final-year students. Addressing these barriers through structured interventions can help

help reduce anxiety and improve academic outcomes.

6.0 RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Integrate time management workshops into the college orientation program starting in the 2025/2026 academic session, with at least two sessions per semester facilitated by the Guidance and Counseling Unit.
2. Establish a peer mentorship program by January 2026, pairing each final-year student with a junior mentee and monitoring progress through monthly meetings.
3. Implement academic stress management counseling sessions in the college clinic beginning second semester of 2025/2026, targeting at least 70% student participation annually.
4. Organize mindfulness and relaxation training workshops two weeks before each examination period starting from 2025/2026, facilitated by trained mental health professionals.

7.0 LIMITATIONS

1. The study was limited to one institution, which may reduce generalizability.
2. Self-reported data may be subject to bias.
3. The use of online questionnaires could exclude students with poor internet access.

8.0 SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

1. Conduct similar studies across multiple institutions in Nigeria.
2. Compare time management effectiveness between diploma and degree nursing students.
3. Explore the impact of mobile technology usage on academic performance and stress.

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